

**RESEARCH ON SALARY MANAGEMENT OPTIMIZATION STRATEGY OF LIJIANG YULONG
TOURISM CO., LTD**

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Abstract

This study examines the compensation management practices of Lijiang Yulong Tourism Co., Ltd. through a lens of equity theory, employing methods such as salary surveys and team interviews to identify existing issues. The findings reveal optimization potential in both internal equity and external equity dimensions. Building on these insights, the paper proposes actionable recommendations for enhancing compensation management systems, aiming to support the company's high-quality development in the tourism sector.

Keywords: equity theory; compensation management; optimization strategy.

I. Background

With the booming development of China's tourism industry, the number of tourists continues to grow, and their demands for travel experiences are increasingly personalized and sophisticated. As a labor-intensive sector that relies on human resources and primarily generates profits through service delivery, the tourism industry faces growing talent shortages. To address this challenge, tourism enterprises are employing various strategies to attract and retain professionals. Effective compensation incentive mechanisms are crucial in unlocking workforce potential and creating greater value. This study focuses on Lijiang Yulong Tourism Co., Ltd., a company that holds a significant position in Yunnan's tourism market.

Lijiang Yulong Tourism Co., Ltd. has accumulated substantial experience in brand marketing and operational management. However, the company remains in the exploratory phase of internal management, particularly in human resources. Key challenges include recruitment difficulties, an aging workforce, subpar employee competency levels, limited career advancement opportunities, and struggles to retain top talent. The root cause of these issues lies in insufficient emphasis on compensation management within the organization.

II. THEORETICAL RESEARCH

2.1 Research on salary management

In compensation management, numerous scholars have conducted in-depth research and empirical studies. Joseph J. Martocchio (2002) argued that traditional compensation systems only increase income through promotions, rather than based on comprehensive individual capabilities. Replacing the conventional hierarchical and narrow-range compensation structure with a

more flexible, multi-tiered system could better motivate employees who struggle to advance. By designing salary adjustment criteria from multiple perspectives, such reforms could enhance workforce motivation. Lopez-Cabrales (2006) discovered that core employees play a vital role in corporate development. Compensation systems can attract these key personnel and sustain their enthusiasm, maximizing human resource efficiency. Many scholars also contend that traditional compensation evaluation operates as an isolated system disconnected from organizational strategic objectives. The new compensation framework addresses this gap, effectively aligning with organizational goals.

Pei Yulin (2018) proposed that compensation management serves as a vital mechanism for enterprises to stimulate employee motivation and creativity. Effective compensation management is essential for sustainable corporate development. To achieve this, companies must establish a compensation optimization process encompassing compensation strategies, job analysis, position evaluation, and compensation surveys, along with relevant systems and plans. This approach enhances operational stability and sustainability while improving the incentive effectiveness and rationality of compensation structures. Liu Yujuan (2022) emphasized that compensation management constitutes the core of human resource management and represents an inevitable choice for enterprises to unleash employees' innovative potential. Therefore, developing standardized, scientific, and adaptive compensation systems that align with corporate development needs is a crucial path for sustainable growth.

2.2 Fairness Theory Research

In 1965, American behavioral scientist Adams proposed the Equity Theory, which suggests that employees unconsciously compare their rewards with both

their own past efforts and those of others. Yin Lu (2018) emphasized that compensation serves as a concrete reflection of employee performance and is closely tied to job satisfaction, while also being a crucial component of human resource management. Li Yan (2020) further noted that the fairness of compensation practices significantly influences employee work performance.

Liu Na (2021) noted that corporate compensation systems are the result of comprehensive consideration of various practical factors, making it impossible for two identical systems to exist. However, the practical significance of applying equity theory to corporate compensation management lies in holistically evaluating fairness factors across three dimensions: external, internal, and individual employee aspects. This approach helps refine compensation management systems, attract and retain top talent, genuinely stimulate employees' intrinsic motivation and work enthusiasm, thereby promoting the enterprise's long-term sustainable development. Wei Zhilin et al. (2016) suggested that compensation equity perception plays a significant mediating role between psychological compensation discount and work performance.

III. Current situation of salary management of Lijiang Yulong Tourism Co., LTD

3.1 The actual income of employees does not match the income announced by external recruitment

In its current external recruitment practices, Lijiang Yulong Tourism Co., Ltd. typically describes compensation packages as "negotiable" or "including annual bonuses and irregular rewards," without specifying clear annual salary ranges or total annual leave

provisions. This results in a high proportion of variable compensation within the company's structure. Consequently, while the annual income disclosed in job postings appears modest, the actual earnings after employment demonstrate a strong competitive edge for prospective candidates. This compensation structure results in a mismatch between employees' actual income and the advertised salaries on external recruitment platforms, making it challenging to attract top talent quickly in the job market. While the basic monthly salary at Lijiang Yulong Tourism Co., Ltd. appears to lag behind market standards—significantly lower than similar companies—its comprehensive annual compensation package places it in the upper-middle range, offering a competitive edge in the industry.

3.2 The structure and payment method of floating compensation do not match the industry practice

The floating compensation of Lijiang Yulong Tourism Co., Ltd. is roughly divided into performance-based (performance bonus), overtime pay, bonus and welfare. The welfare covers a wide range of projects and has a large amount of advantages, but the payment method is not in line with the industry practice, resulting in the imbalance of employees' income in the off-season and peak season, and employees are only very satisfied with the salary in some months.

As can be seen from Table 1, in July, August and October, the comprehensive income of employees of Lijiang Yulong Tourism Co., Ltd. can reach about 7,000 yuan, but the income in ordinary months is only about 3,000 yuan, while the income of other types of tourist attractions and service enterprises is relatively average in each month, and the gap is not obvious.

Table 1

Comparison of Floating Compensation Structures and Amounts (Based on Grassroots Positions)

Item	Lijiang Yulong Tourism Co., LTD	Other travel companies
Performance-based pay base	About 600 yuan/month	/
Overtime pay	Disbursed as actually paid	Disbursed as actually paid
Holiday bonus	About 500 yuan per year	Sent holiday gifts or bonuses
October Golden Week Subsidy	3000 yuan/person	/
Summer vacation season bonus	100 to 180 yuan per person per day	/
Year-end bonus	4,000 yuan per person	5,000 to 8,000 yuan per person

3.3 There is little difference between the salary of technical personnel and other positions

Lijiang Yulong Tourism Co., Ltd. categorizes its workforce into three main divisions: technical operations, service operations, and general management. While the technical operations division has the smallest workforce, it faces the most recruitment challenges, exhibits lower employee retention rates, and offers higher salaries to new hires compared to some veteran staff. The company's internal compensation system for technical personnel lacks fairness, and the pay gap between technical roles and other positions remains relatively narrow.

IV. OPTIMIZATION STRATEGIES

4.1 Adjust the compensation distribution model to align internal compensation with market compensation

By strategically adjusting the ratio of fixed to variable compensation through a "one-up-one-down" approach based on market research data, companies can maintain competitive monthly income levels relative to industry benchmarks, thereby enhancing recruitment appeal. Simultaneously, increased fixed compensation will improve employees' perceived compensation value.

4.2 Establish a compensation framework for technical and operational roles to achieve balanced internal compensation within the enterprise

Tailored to the unique demands of technical roles, the company has established a dual-track compensation system featuring both career advancement and professional skill enhancement. This framework empowers employees to choose development paths that align with their personality traits, skill levels, and organizational

needs. The dual-track system also addresses the issue of limited promotion channels by allowing employees to earn salary increases through skill development when administrative vacancies are scarce.

To ensure fair and impartial performance evaluations, tourism enterprises should refine their assessment methods. Since many service aspects can not be quantified, most companies currently rely on metrics like tourist numbers and ticket revenue. However, such single-dimensional indicators fail to comprehensively reflect employee performance. Therefore, businesses should develop a holistic evaluation system tailored to tourism services, providing fair assessments and implementing appropriate rewards or penalties based on actual contributions.

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